

Analytical and Characterisation Excellence in nanomaterial risk assessment: A tiered approach

Grant Agreement No 720952

Deliverable Report 4.2

Deliverable	D4.2 Guideline for Method and Protocol Standardization
Work Package	WP4: Linking ontology and methodology
Delivery date	M18 - 30 June 2018
Lead Beneficiary	Sveriges Lantbruksuniversitet (SLU)
Nature of Deliverable	Report
Dissemination Level	Public (PU)

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Introduction

All experiments or routine monitoring of nanoparticles (NPs) result in some form of characterisation data of them embedded in certain matrices. For toxicological testing, for instance, the concentration measured as *e.g.* particle number or surface area per volume is very important for setting up dose-response curves. There is a desire to create databases of such results that would allow building quantitative nano-structure activity relationships (QNSAR). Such modelling is the most cost-efficient way of assessing risks of new NPs, because their diversity increases exponentially and systematic testing would therefore be prohibitively expensive. This approach has moreover been very successful for conventional chemicals, albeit only in some well-defined classes of chemicals.

Contrary to conventional chemicals, more parameters than the molecular structure and mass concentration are required to define NPs. It is common to characterise many NP properties during experiments, such as size, composition, or organic coating. These properties are called endpoints for the sake of this deliverable, in analogy with those quantified during toxicological experiments where it means the effect a chemical or NP has on the test organism.

Correct interpretation of an endpoint requires much more than the value itself. It is widely known that many of the characterisation techniques for NPs impose artefacts that depend on the sample preparation steps, and also on the instrumental settings chosen. Moreover, traditional analytical qualities such as precision, accuracy, resolution all affect correct interpretation of a NP endpoint. Many NP characterisation techniques are also oblique towards certain NP properties. It is hence imperative to know the influences on and limitations of each specific technique and report them as metadata of the experiment. If this metadata to an endpoint is not collected, the efficiency of a QNSAR attempt drops dramatically, or larger amounts of data would be required to discover significant trends, because in lack of relevant data there is a significant part of the variance that cannot be assigned to its source.

Previous data-collection attempts have often used spreadsheets having several fields for collecting the characterisation data and metadata of an experiment. Having too few fields, vital metadata will be omitted, while too many irrelevant fields will demotivate the data provider from entering all pertinent information available. Ideally, the number of fields filled out equals the amount of data required for assessment of measurement quality, but this cannot be realised in a non-flexible spreadsheet format. Previous initiatives to amass NP data for QNSAR have thus only partly collected the full measure of metadata that is required for correct interpretation of NP endpoints.

A first thought-line was therefore to gather protocols via open-question questionnaires. These could thus be stored in a database and attached to data entered by the user. However, such questionnaire would have to change constantly, i.e. a questionnaire would have to be designed for each end point determined with each technique to gather precisely the information that is required, not too much and not too little. Moreover, the questionnaire would have to be adapted each time new insights on protocols are gained, or a new technique is developed.

Instead, a different strategy was chosen that is indeed flexible enough to easily accommodate new techniques – also in the future. Questionnaires would be generated automatically when users want to add data, calling for the metadata, i.e. the measurement protocol. The questionnaire would ask only those parameters that are absolutely required for correct data interpretation whilst providing default values to guide the user. The default values would, however, not be stored in the protocol as this would distort possible data interpretation. This approach ensures the user is not demotivated and maximizes the chance that all required metadata is collected. It is clear that this requirement calls for analysis of the metalogic behind any thinkable questionnaire to achieve generality, based upon which

a questionnaire can be automatically generated after providing some basic information about the technique.

The goal of the current deliverable was therefore to construct an interactive system ensuring:

1. Flexibility of the system so that new measurement insights or new techniques can be added easily
2. Collection of enough data and metadata to ensure current and future interpretation of NP characterisation data without the burden of collecting and storing superfluous information
3. Creation of a protocol database
4. Automatic coupling of obtained data and protocols via ontologies

The goal of this system is thus two-fold: To collect data on NP characterisation and at the same time collect all relevant metadata for correct interpretation of these data. Protocols would thus be collected at the same time in a database, so that different users can reselect them when they enter new data that was collected in exactly the same way or allow the user to slightly adjust the protocol if the data was gathered in a slightly different way.

There are **sample preparation** protocols, **measurement**, and **data treatment** protocols, and all have implications in how an endpoint value should be interpreted. Using the higher-level logic approach, requirement 3 can be reached by allowing data providers to store all their metadata, which includes sample pre-treatment, in different protocols. This has as the advantage that these protocols can be uploaded when a similar measurement is done, again in an attempt not to discourage the data provider. Moreover, an automated questionnaire can be linked to measurement files from the instrument software, thus possibly allowing to automatically fill out much of the metadata.

Finally, an automated system could easily be connected to software and thereby also to databases reaching requirement 4 provided that the metadata fields are linked with ontologies.

The goals set out above were reached as follows :

1. The metadata contributing to a correct interpretation of NP characterisation data was analysed and structured into an object-oriented hierarchy. This logic is described in the main body of this deliverable.
2. The ACEnano project partners were asked to each provide essential information of their technique of expertise. This information is stored in an **internal database** that is used to assist users of the user interface.
3. Based on the analysis in step 1, the user interface was created at Douglas Connect. This user interface auto-generates questionnaires based on the logic outlined below and based on the internal database containing essential information on each technique.
4. The partners were then asked to test the software by adding their measurement data and providing feedback.
5. The software was then optimised and made available.

The interface will be continuously improved, ie. its state will likely change beyond the details laid out in this Deliverable, both during the lifetime of ACEnano and beyond. The latter is possible by integrating the tool with other data storage initiatives (e.g. NanoCommons), but also by allowing users to give feedback on-line on functionalities of the tool using an on-line form.

Logic

Main elements

Three main parts are shown in Figure 1

- An **internal database** basically containing different predefined protocols as well as expert insights in to what is relevant during specific measurements
- The **analysis protocol**: This is all relevant metadata that is deemed pertinent for one or more measurements. The internal database stores amongst others such analysis protocols.
- The **data** obtained by the user, consisting of raw data that is then interpreted into treated data. The ACEnano knowledge warehouse is eventually meant to also store the data created by users together with the metadata stemming from the interactive tool described here.

Much of the information stored within the internal database is specific for **combinations of endpoints measured with a specific technique**. An endpoint may be measured by several techniques, and a certain technique may be capable of measuring several endpoints and each of these combinations has specific requirements upon the technique, sample preparation, and possibly even algorithms.

Internal database

The internal database has two purposes:

1. to guide the user to filling in information
2. to allow the user to reuse previously completed protocols.

The first type of information was deemed specific to individual combinations of endpoints and techniques. It helps the user at different stages when completing analysis protocols as indicated by the red arrows in Figure 1. Most of this information was gathered from questionnaires sent out to experts in their respective techniques. Stored information comprises:

- Possible endpoint/technique combinations (see Table 9).
- Information on these combinations
 - which kind of samples can be measured
 - what are the relevant instrument settings that make a difference when interpreting NP characterisation data
 - what quality parameters are produced
 - which compounds may interfere with the measurement
 - what are possible algorithm steps to treat raw data
- Possible sample preparation steps such as dispersing, sonicating, weighing, that constitute the sample preparation routine (See Table 10)
- Possible units usable for various numbers of the metadata

The second type of stored information are previously defined protocols that can be uploaded at several stages when entering metadata to speed up entering this data. The user can, however, still choose to change certain parameters of the protocol. In this case, the link to a standard protocol is remembered, but a new “variant” is created. The database also serves as a resource for people to learn about standard protocols, i.e. before they start doing their measurements. In some cases, e.g. when entering replicates for the same measurement, the whole analysis protocol can just be tagged to each measurement, but in many other cases, smaller parts of this analysis protocol are to be reused:

1. *Standard media*. The sample chemistry plays an important role in determining artefacts during measurement of nanoparticle properties. The user is given the opportunity to select from a list of standard media (e.g. algal medium), e.g. when choosing a sample preparation action “dispersion in medium”.
2. *Sample preparation protocols*. Milling, sonicating, shaking, dilution can all have a profound effect on many endpoints of NPs and this information therefore needs to be stored. For this reason, much effort has already been undertaken by OECD and FP7 EU projects to standardise exactly these protocols.
3. *Measurement protocols*: As for sample preparation protocols, there are also standard measurement protocols, often also known as “Standard operating procedures” (SOPs). Similarly, the user can select one of these and then alter certain parameters.

Figure 1. Logic of the database showing the three main parts. The internal database of expert knowledge and protocols, a more detailed view of the analysis protocol where all metadata for a measurement is stored and finally the data itself. The analysis protocol also shows the chronology of how information is fed into the interactive tool.

Analysis protocol

Figure 1 shows the chronology of how information on analysis protocols is provided by users into the user interface.

1. The user will first indicate which endpoint/technique combination has been used.
2. The user subsequently gives some general info on the sample, such as what phase it is (a solid powder, suspension, ...) and the *nanoparticle* being measured. In most cases, the user knows exactly which nanoparticle is in the sample, but in some cases, the whole purpose of a measurement is to find out what sort of nanoparticle is in the sample (e.g. analysis of environmental samples). In this case, the nanoparticle is unknown, but any information the user can give is stored together with the endpoint measured.
3. Within the *sample preparation phase* of the data collection flow, information is stored about the *original sample*, and the actions taken to make the *prepared sample* ready for measurement.
4. Information is then collected about the actual measurement. A *combination* was selected at step 1. This object contains information about the used instrument, and the parameters and

settings used for this *endpoint/technique* combination that are relevant for the specific *endpoint* being measured.

5. Use of this technique with certain technique parameters stored in the object *technique parameters* produces a *raw dataset*.
6. The user will also provide the data treatment *algorithms* used for data analysis and the parameters of these *algorithms*. There are default values provided for those parameters that seldom differ from the most common ones to ease entering of data.
7. The data treatment *algorithms* then transform *raw data* into *treated data*, and thus also the final measured and processed value(s) of the endpoint.

The user is guided through entering the metadata, thus preventing the user from entering a measurement of dubious quality. For instance, when entering the information stored about samples (*Original sample* and *Prepared sample* in Figure 1), the user is prompted to choose from the phases that are deemed possible to measure with the technique chosen, and to state values for those chemical and physical parameters of the nanoparticles and their matrix that are known to influence the measurement. In addition, it is checked by the user interface that the order of sample preparation actions (milling, shaking, sonicating, ...) indeed transforms phases in a correct fashion, providing a prepared sample that can indeed be measured by the chosen technique. For instance, milling cannot be done on an aqueous sample and a powdered sample cannot be measured by single particle ICP-MS. Checks and balances are also built in at the data treatment stage. The user has to provide the algorithm steps step-by-step. The user is thus compelled to report the complete set of parameters affecting a measurement while the database will not be burdened by irrelevant information.

Data

The user interface allows to store data in very flexible formats, because especially raw data can be very complex and varying from e.g. single values to multi-dimensional data or images. The possibility is also there to upload output files created by instrument software. This is likely the most accurate way of uploading data, but it would require that instrument manufacturers also allow extracting certain portions of these data files. The user is also asked to provide uncertainties and/or measurement qualities (as defined by the *technique*) that can be multi-dimensional as well. Detection limits are also asked for to make it possible to assess whether the measurement could have been oblique for certain particle populations.

Object oriented structure

The full set of classes and their hierarchy is described in Tables 1-3. The items in these tables are object oriented classes. Each class stores information as its properties. These properties can in turn be classes or arrays of classes having their properties. There is thus a hierarchy of classes that makes up the internal database (Table 2). Such structured data can be much easier queried compared to data that is stored e.g. in a spreadsheet format. Object oriented programming assigns methods to classes that can be used for guiding the user through answering questionnaires correctly and imposing restrictions. Another useful feature of object-oriented programming is inheritance. A superclass can be created with some properties and methods. Then, subclasses can be created. Objects belonging to these subclasses inherit all properties and methods from this superclass and additional properties and methods can be added that slightly change the behaviour of objects of these subclasses relatively from the superclass objects. This was used here in one instance. Table 1 describes the superclass “protocol” which has several subclasses:

- analysisprotocol: the all-encompassing protocol holding all the metadata for an analysis
- samplepreparationprotocol: only sample preparation steps involved
- measurementprotocol: only measurement and data treatment settings are involved
- standardmedium: only the chemistry for a sample’s medium is listed.

It is indicated that these classes are subclasses of “protocol” with a symbol “<” in Table 2. This means that they also have the properties shown in Table 1 in addition to those shown in Table 2.

Table 1. The protocol superclass and its properties

class	properties	class	Description
protocol	name	string	the name of this standard measurement protocol
	description	string	a short description of this measurement protocol
	protocolversion	protocolversion	the version of the measurement protocol
protocolversion	version	integer	the version of this protocol
	variant	integer	the variant number. The measurement protocol was possibly derived from an earlier measurement protocol
	derivedfrom	measurement protocol	the measurement protocol this protocol was derived from. IF this property is empty the variant should be 1
	developmentphase	string	The development phase this particular standard is at (“research phase”, “validated”, “ingtest”, “ISO standard”, “OECD standard”)
	organisation	string	organisation that created this measurement protocol

	confidentiality	string	the level of confidentiality, can be "public", "private", "aceno", "my organisation"
	license	string	the license number of the measurement protocol
	contactperson	person	the contact person for this measurement protocol. Can be taken directly from the user profile of the Knowledge Warehouse account as a default
	otherpersons	array of person	other persons involved in making this protocol
person	first name	string	first name of a contact person
	last name	string	last name of a contact person
	email	string	email of a contact person
	role	string	role of a contact person in an organisation

Table 2 below lists all of the classes that make up the internal database as well as the properties that these classes have. This database comprises

- endpoints;
- techniques and all the different settings, default values that could be set;
- applicable combinations of endpoints and techniques to measure them;
- samplepreparation options such as a list of actions that can be taken when preparing nanoparticle containing sample for analysis. Also included are standard media one could wish to select;
- applicable units in different cases;
- protocols of the four types mentioned.

Table 3 comprises the classes that are stored for a specific instance of an analysis. An array of such analysis objects thus comprises a database of analysis. Each instance will have an analysis protocol associated with it as metadata as well as possibly raw data as well as treated data.

Again, it is important to note that few properties, default values, default units, etc. are specific to a particular endpoint or technique. Most is made specific for a particular combination of an endpoint measured by a specific technique.

Table 2 and Table 3 also indicate how the communication with the internal database occurs during use of the user interface to compose protocols, but this is also explained in much more detailed further down.

Table 2. Properties of the internal database. Numerical values entered by the administrators are generally stored as the datatype ``double``, and text as ``string``, and logical values given as a response to yes/no, present/not present type of questions are assigned the type ``Boolean``. The actual values for the internal database for the first version of the tool are given in appendix.

class	properties	Class	description
internaldatabase	endpoints	array of endpoint	all possible endpoints
	techniques	array of technique	all possible techniques
	combinations	array of combination	list of all possible endpoint-technique combinations
	sampleprep	Sampleprep	All stored properties for sample preparation
	units	Unitclass	All different units possible to use in different situations
	analysisprotocols	Analysisprotocol	The predefined analysis protocols that can be consulted
endpoint	name	String	The name of the endpoint. The currently possible ones can be found in Table 9
technique	possiblephases	array of string	The phases that this technique can accept. This constricts which type of prepared samples can be measured using this technique. If the prepared sample has the wrong phase, an error should be generated.
	settings	array of setting	All possible settings for this technique (having empty values for the property "value")
	measurement quality parameters	array of measurementqualityparameter	All possible measurement quality parameters for this technique
	models	array of string	The names of possible instruments that can be used for this technique
combination	endpoint	Endpoint	the endpoint of this endpoint/technique combination

	technique	Technique	the technique of this endpoint/technique combination
	measurementprotocols	array of measurementprotocol cols	Here a list of measurement protocols (also called SOP) is stored for this particular endpoint/technique combination. These only hold values for those technique settings that are relevant for the user to fill out for this particular endpoint/technique combination. They come from the technique.settings property, but the property "value" is not empty now as it contains default values.
	relevantchemistry	Chemistry	This object has empty values for those chemistry parameters not relevant for this combination. Relevant parameters are either arrays from which the user can select or have a default value that shows that they are relevant. See further for properties of the class chemistry.
	relevantmeasurementqualityparameters	array of string	All the relevant measurement quality parameters (without actual values) for this particular endpoint/technique combination.
	possiblealgorithms	array of algorithm	the possible algorithm steps one can do with the data generated by this technique for this particular endpoint/technique combination.
	LOD_lower	Double	default values for the lower limit of detection. Units are in LOD_units
	LOD_upper	Double	default values for the upper limit of detection. Units are in LOD_units
	LOD_units	String	units of the LOD. Is one of the units found within the property "combination.possibleunits"
	possibledatasets	array of dataset (see Table 3)	Templates for the possible types of data that can be obtained for this combination.
sampleprep	phases	array of string	all possible phases that can be selected, e.g. "liquid", "solid"

	actions	array of action	actions that can be selected when defining the sample treatment protocol
	compounds	array of compound	some predefined compounds to choose from when defining the sample media
	particles	array of compound	some predefined (non-nanoparticle) particles to choose from when defining the sample media (e.g. clays, iron oxides...)
	matrix	array of compounds	some predefined possible matrices (water, plastic...)
	smallcompounds	array of compounds	some predefined proteins and small compounds to select from when defining the sample media
	celltypes	array of string	some predefined cell types to select from when defining the sample media
	antibiotics	array of string	some predefined antibiotics to select from when defining the sample media
	dyes	array of compounds	some predefined dyes to select from when defining the sample media
	samplepreparationp rotocols	array of samplepreparationprotocols	some predefined sample preparation protocols
	standardmedia	array of chemistry	some predefined standard media
unitclass	uncertaintytypes	array of string	the different types of uncertainty to use
	concentration	array of string	the possible units to use. Note that this depends on the phase of the medium
	time	array of string	the possible units to use for time
	dimension	array of string	the possible units to use for dimensions
	surfacearea	array of string	the possible units to use for surface area
	name	String	name of the standard sample preparation protocol

samplepreparation protocol < protocol	protocolversion	Protocolversion	version of the protocol
	actions	array of actions	the actions defining this standard protocol
compound	name	String	Name of the compound
	concentration	Double	concentration of the compound
	concentrationunits	String	the concentration units, chosen from internaldatabase.unitclass.concentration. Which concentration that can be selected depends on the phase of the medium
standardmedium < protocol	chemistry	Chemistry	the chemistry of the standard medium
action	name	string	Name of the action
	amplitudeormedium	String	is “amplitude” or “medium” to indicate whether this concerns an action with an amplitude (e.g. centrifugation) or an action like dispersion, that has no amplitude but has instead a medium in which the nanoparticle is immersed.
	amplitudename	string	term to express the intensity of the action (Table 10)
	order	integer	the order of the action in a series of actions composing a sample preparation protocol
	amplitude	array of settings	amplitude settings
	medium	chemistry	the composition of the medium used e.g. for the action “dispersion” (Table 10)
	startphase	string	allowed startphase of the sample on which this action is performed. Chosen from internaldatabase.sampleprep.phases

	endphase	string	endphase of the sample when this action is finished. Chosen from internaldatabase.sampleprep.phases
setting	name	string	name of this particular setting
	value	integer/double/string/boolean	value of the setting
	possible values	array of integer/double/string/boolean	possible value of the settings
	units	string	units of this setting
	possibleunits	array of string	the units possible to choose from for this particular setting
analysisprotocol < protocol	combination	technique	the endpoint/technique combination for which data is to be stored to be chosen from internaldatabase.combinations
	orginalsample	sample	the sample at the very start of the analysis
	preparedsample	sample	the sample's condition after preparation and prior to the actual analysis
	samplepreparation	samplepreparation	the samplepreparation protocol. Either filled out from scratch or selected from internaldatabase.combination.standardprotocols
	techniquesettings	techniquesettings	all the settings of the analysis.
	algorithm	algorithm	the data treatment algorithm(s) and their default settings to be selected from internaldatabase.combination.possiblealgorithms
sample	phase	string	the phase of this sample to be selected from internaldatabase.sampleprep.phases

	chemistry	chemistry	The detailed chemistry of the matrix. To be selected from internaldatabase.sampleprep.standardmedia
	nanoparticle	array of nanoparticle	All properties of the nanoparticle(s) being measured of which the user is aware
	standardmedium	standardmedium	To be selected from internaldatabase.sampleprep.standardmedia. There are three possibilities for this property 1. empty: a medium was given by the user starting from scratch. 2. the actions listed in the property “chemistry” is equal to the the actions listed in this protocol: The user used the standard medium without additions or changes. 3. the chemistry s listed in the property “chemistry” is different from the the chemistry listed in this standardmedium: The actually used chemistry was based on the one of this standard medium
nanoparticle	composition	array of compound	The chemical composition of the nanoparticle
	concentration	double	The concentration of the nanoparticle in the sample
	concentrationunits	string	units of concentration. To be selected from internaldatabase.unitclass.concentration where the choice depends on sample.phase
	coating	array of compound	Chemical composition of the coating
	dimensions	array of double	dimensions of the nanoparticle
	sizemeasurand	sizemeasurandtype	what the dimensions mean
	sizeunits	sizeunitstype	unit of the dimensions. To be selected from internaldatabase.unitclass.dimension

	crystalline phase	string	crystalline structure of the NP core
	surface area	double	surface area. To be selected from internaldatabase.unitclass.surfacearea
	area units	areaunits type	units of the surface area. To be selected from internaldatabase.unitclass.surfacearea
	coating thickness	double	thickness of the coating. Same units as the property "sizeunits"
samplepreparation	protocol	array of action	The different actions that were taken to go from the original sample to the prepared sample
	standardprotocol	standardprotocol	To be selected from internaldatabase.sampleprep.standardprotocols. There are three possibilities for this property 1. empty: a protocol was given by the user starting from scratch. 2. the actions listed in the property "protocol" is equal to the the actions listed in this protocol: The user used on of the standard protocol to the fullest (relevant) detail 3. the actions listed in the property "protocol" is different from the the actions listed in this protocol: The actually used protocol was based on this standard protocol
chemistry	pH	double	the pH of the sample, in principle this is only relevant for aqueous samples, but is often also a standard parameters for e.g. soils or sludges. A default value is taken from internaldatabase.combination.relevantchemistry.pH
	compounds	array of compound	The basic compounds relevant for aggregation of nanoparticles. Which compounds can be selected and their default values are taken from internaldatabase.combination.relevantchemistry.compounds
	interfering compounds	array of compound	compounds that can interfere with the measurement such as elements of the same mass than the nanoparticle for e.g. spICP-MS. Which compounds can be

			selected and their default values are taken from internaldatabase.combination.relevantchemistry.interferingcompounds
preferential orientation	boolean		only relevant for XRD measurement. The default value can be taken from internaldatabase.combination.relevantchemistry.preferentialorientation, but if this value is empty this option is not shown.
other particles	array of compound		interfering particles such as clays. The default value can be taken from internaldatabase.combination.relevantchemistry.otherparticles, but if this value is empty this option is not shown.
matrix	chemistry		for aqueous samples this is water, but can be a solvent or plastic if the nanoparticles re mebedded in a plastic. Default value is selected from internaldatabase.combination.relevantchemistry.matrix
permittivity	double		only relevant for aqueous phase chemistry. The units are unitless as the permittivity is relative towards the one of vacuum. Note that user seldom know this, but this can also be calculated from the detailed chemistry they give. The default value can be taken from internaldatabase.combination.relevantchemistry.permittivity, but if this value is empty this option is not shown.
smallmolecules	array of compound		Specific proteins or small organic molecules can be given here if they are relevant to know about. For environmental samples, the dissolved organic carbon concentration should not be given here, but as a compound. The default value can be taken from internaldatabase.combination.relevantchemistry.smallmolecules, but if this value is empty this option is not shown.
celltype	string		Only relevant if the phase is "cell" (e.g. human a549). The default value can be taken from internaldatabase.combination.relevantchemistry.celltype, but if this value is empty this option is not shown.

	medium	chemistry	Sometimes, the nanoparticles are dispersed in a first medium (e.g. cells) that are then dispersed in a second medium. This allows giving this extra information. The default value can be taken from <code>internaldatabase.combination.relevantchemistry.medium</code> , but if this value is empty this option is not shown.
	antibiotics	array of compound	Relevant for analysis involving microbiota. The default value can be taken from <code>internaldatabase.combination.relevantchemistry.antibiotics</code> , but if this value is empty this option is not shown.
	dyes	array of compound	Relevant for calorimetric tests. The default value can be taken from <code>internaldatabase.combination.relevantchemistry.dyes</code> , but if this value is empty this option is not shown.
techniquesettings	instrumentmodel	array of string	the specific instruments used
	settings	array of setting	The different settings that were used for the selected technique to go from the prepared sample towards the raw dataset
	sop	sop	To be selected from <code>internaldatabase.sops</code> . There are three possibilities for this property 1. empty: all settings were given by the user starting from scratch. 2. the settings listed in the property "settings" are equal to the the settings listed in this sop: The user used one of the sops to the fullest (relevant) detail 3. the settings listed in the property "settings" are different from the the settings listed in this sop: The actually used settings were based on this sop
algorithm	algorithm parameters	array of settings	The relevant Algorithm parameters. They are, for each technique-endpoint combination, listed in table A6.
	order	integer	The order that this algorithm is performed in the chain of algorithms used to go from raw to treated data.

Table 3. All classes related to a specific analysis

class	properties	class	description
analysis	analysisprotocol	analysisprotocol	the analysis protocol used for this analysis, i.e. all the metadata associated with this analysis
	rawdataset	dataset	the raw dataset produced by the analysis
	treateddataset	dataset	the final treated data as interpreted by algorithms
dataset	name	string	The name of a data set is automatically generated based on the content of dataset.axes.axes.name
	measurements	axes	In the simplest case, there is only a single value or maybe a few replicate values for a particular analysis but to be as flexible as possible a multidimensional matrix of numerical values should be possible to be able to e.g. accommodate 3D images, which requires several axes.
	uncertainty	axes	The database should be flexible enough to give an uncertainty value for each measured value, but this is rarely so and often there is only one uncertainty value for a given dataset
	uncertaintytype	string	How to interpret the uncertainty values. To be selected from internaldatabase.unitclass.uncertaintytypes.
	measurement qualityparameter	axes	Some techniques also provide measurement quality parameters The database should be flexible enough to give a measurement quality parameter for each measured value, but this is rarely so and often there is only one uncertainty value for a given dataset
	qualityparameter type	string	How to interpret the quality parameters. To be selected from internaldatabase.combination.relevantmeasurementqualityparameters

	lod_lower	double	Lower limit of detection achieved during measurement. A default value is suggested from internaldatabase.combination.LOD_lower
	lod_upper	double	Upper limit of detection achieved during measurement. A default value is suggested from internaldatabase.combination.LOD_upper
axes	axes	array of axis	The different axes constituting this data
	type	string	The type of data for this axis. Four possible values: "single value", "text", "image", "output of instrument software"
	file	file	file containing the data for this axis. This can be a text or image file or a file from instrument software.
axis	name	string	name of the variable
	valueaxis	boolean	if true, this means that this axis are the dependent variables, otherwise it concerns an axis of independent variables.
	values	array of double	the values of this axis
	units	string	chosen from axis.possibleunits
	possibleunits	string	all possible unti for this particular axis
	startcolumn	integer	start column for axis data when coming from a text file
	endcolumn	integer	end column for axis data when coming from a text file
	startrow	integer	start row for axis data when coming from a text file
	endrow	integer	end row for axis data when coming from a text file

User interface programming

An obvious observation from the analysis protocol class in Table 2 is that a large amount of metadata seems to be required with each measured value. To motivate users to still provide all this information, it was chosen to develop an interactive tool rather than having users fill out extensive excel files. All of the metadata is therefore entered interactively responding to questions presented by a user interface. This interface also allows constricting the number of possible choices to the relevant ones, thus guiding the user and minimizing inconsistencies. The following tables contain the logic behind the questions asked by the interface and the choices of answers presented to the user, together with instructions for the programmers for which specific datatypes the answers should be assigned to and which class properties they set. This was the way of communicating the analysis of the tool (done by partner SLU) towards the programmers (at partner DC).

There are forms that need filling in the following order:

1. General questions about the analysis protocol (Table 4)
2. Sample preparation (Table 5)
3. Analysis details and algorithm (Table 6)
4. A form (Table 7) on how measurement data can be entered.

Headings are indicated in the tables by gray bands. There are five columns in these tables

1. The first column is just a number to which sometimes is referred to
2. This column shows the "question" that is asked, i.e. the property that is sought. If the value of a particular property should be reflected in the text of the question itself, that property is placed within "#".
3. This column indicates codes to indicate which type of question is asked and what the possible answers are.
 - "1N": Multiple choice - only one choice possible - NO additional free text other
 - "MN": Multiple choice - more than one choice possible - NO additional free text other
 - "1W" Multiple choice - only one choice possible - WITH additional free text other
 - "MW" Multiple choice - more than one choice possible - WITH additional free text other
 - "FS" Free text - string
 - "FN" Free text numeric
 - [other]: means a free text can be filled in if none of the available options is relevant. These are then added to the Choices, the next time another or the same user does this questionnaire.
 - "X" means it is non-editable
4. The choices that are presented to the user (if any). Here, the internal database is used often to guide the user in selecting relevant answers.
5. The last column is for remarks. "⇒" means that the answer fills out a particular property of Table 2, shown as the name of the class to which the property belongs followed by a dot (".") and then the name of the property itself. Other behaviours of the tool are also described in this column.

Table 4. “General Info”: General questions about the analysis protocol being created.

Nr	Question	Type	Choices	Remarks
1	Protocol name	FS		⇒ analysisprotocol.name
2	Brief description	FS		⇒ analysisprotocol.description
3	Protocol version	1W	<p>Three fields are shown:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Version – X • Variant – X • Derived from – 1W internaldatabase.analysisprotocols.name. <p>An option [new] must be there too to start a protocol from scratch.</p>	<p>The behaviour varies according to what is selected at “Derived from”</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>If a previously created analysis protocol is selected:</i> the selected analysisprotocol is copied to a new instance. The analysisprotocol.protocolversion.version number remains the same, but the variant is increased with one. • <i>If new is selected:</i> an empty analysis protocol is created. analysisprotocol.protocolversion.version and variant is set to 1. Derived from is set the same name as the protocol.
4	development phase	1N	“research phase”, “validated”, “ingtest”, “ISO standard”, “OECD standard”	⇒ analysisprotocol. protocolversion.developmentphase. In this version a protocol is either an ISO standard or an OECD standard because there will always be at least minor differences between either protocols.
5	Organisation	FS		⇒ analysisprotocol. protocolversion.organisation
6	Confidentiality	1N	“public”, “private”, “acenano”, “my organisation”	⇒ analysisprotocol. protocolversion.confidentiality
7	License	1N		⇒ analysisprotocol. protocolversion.license

8	contact person	FS		⇒ analysisprotocol. protocolversion.contactperson.firstname ⇒ analysisprotocol. protocolversion.contactperson.firstname ⇒ analysisprotocol. protocolversion.contactperson.email ⇒ analysisprotocol. protocolversion.contactperson.role
9	furtherpersons involved	FS	A table appears where further persons involved can be added. 4 fields (first name, last name, email, role) should be in each row. A button needs to be present at the bottom of the table to add new people.	⇒ analysisprotocol.otherpersons(x).firstname ⇒ analysisprotocol. protocolversion.otherpersons(x).firstname ⇒ analysisprotocol. protocolversion.otherpersons(x).email ⇒ analysisprotocol. protocolversion.otherpersons(x).role

Table 5. “Sample preparation”: Questions about sample preparation stage

Nr	Question	Type	Choices	Remarks
Endpoints measured, techniques used				
1		1N	A first box lists internaldatabase.endpoints to choose from. The choices in a second box are limited to all internaldatabase.combinations containing the endpoint selected in 1	⇒ analysisprotocol.combination
Original sample description				
2	Phase	1N	internaldatabase.combination.technique.possiblephases	⇒ analysisprotocol.originalsample.phase
3	Medium	1W	internaldatabase.sampleprep.standardmedia	⇒ analysisprotocol.originalsample.standardmedium

	Select from standard media and/or provide specific detail		[other] (the option to define the samples' chemistry from scratch must always be there)	If a medium is selected, analysisprotocol.originalsample.chemistry = standardmedium.chemistry.
5		MW	internaldatabase.combination.relevantchemistry If the value of this object is empty, the property is not shown to be filled out by the user, otherwise the value is shown as a default value.	⇒ analysisprotocol.originalsample.chemistry This question is always asked, regardless of whether a standard medium was given upon question 4 or not.
6	Save as new medium	X	Button	If clicked, creates a new instance of internaldatabase.standardmedium. A pop-up window appears containing the steps contained in step 7 and 8 if no, skip to question 9
7	see all steps in Table 4 to add a new protocol			⇒ internaldatabase.sampleprep.standardmedia
8	Please review the chemistry of the new medium	MW	A list of ALL chemistry parameters, i.e. not only those that were relevant for the current combination, is shown	⇒ internaldatabase.sampleprep.standardmedia.chemistry ⇒ analysisprotocol.originalsample.standardmedium
9	Was any sample pretreatment done?	1N	Yes/No	If No, preparedsample = originalsample and we skip the whole sample treatment protocol question list
Sample preparation protocol				
10	Select from previously provided standard protocols and/or provide specific details	MW	internaldatabase.sampleprep.samplepreparationprotocols [other] (the option to define the actions from scratch and/or to provide details must always be	⇒ analysisprotocol.samplepreparation.standardprotocol If a sample preparation protocol is selected, analysisprotocol.samplepreparation.protocol equals the selected internaldatabase.sampleprep.standardprotocols.protocol

			there)	and all the actions involved are immediately shown and can be altered by the user.
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11. To define actions, a table should be shown:

Order	Action name	Amplitude/medium	Units	Duration	Units
1	2 – 1N	3 - FN	4 – 1N	5 - FN	6 – 1N

Followed by a button “Add another”. At the end of the last row, there should be a button allowing to delete this action. It is chosen not to add such a button to the end of each row to ensure that actions’ start and endphases are consistent

This table should be used to list all the actions currently present in `analysisprotocol.samplepreparation.protocol`. The choices in the cells of this table should be constrained as follows:

1. Just the array number of the the action within `analysisprotocol.samplepreparation.protocol`
2. Choosing an action here changes the property value of `analysisprotocol.samplepreparation.protocol(end)` with “end” meaning the protocol that is last in the list, i.e. the one being created just now. The actions that can be selected are constricted in two different possible ways:
 - a. *analysisprotocol.samplepreparation.protocol is empty*: showing all the actions from `internaldatabase.sampleprep.actions` for which the property “startphase” equals `analysisprotocol.originalsample.phase`.
 - b. *analysisprotocol.samplepreparation.protocol is NOT empty*: showing all the actions from `internaldatabase.sampleprep.actions` for which the property “startphase” equals `analysisprotocol.samplepreparation.protocol(end-1).endphase`, with “end-1” meaning the action one row up in the table.
3. Two possibilities exist here:
 - a. *The “amplitudeormedium” property of the action chosen in column 2 is “amplitude”*: a free textbox is shown where a numerical value can be entered.
 - b. *The “amplitudeormedium” property of the action chosen in column 2 is “medium”*: the list of `standardmedia` shown in `internaldatabase.sampleprep.standardmedia` with an additional option in the list “define new”. If the latter is shown, a pop-up window appears allowing the user to define the chemistry of a dispersing medium. This window should allow entering those properties of the class “chemistry” (See Table 2), that are not empty in `internaldatabase.combination.relevantchemistry`. The default values of `internaldatabase.combination.relevantchemistry` are shown. A button “OK” at the bottom of this pop-up window allows closing the window and saves the given chemistry as `analysisprotocol.samplepreparation.protocol(end).medium`.
4. Again, two possibilities exist with the same conditions as in point 3:

<p>a. The user can choose from the units listed in the property <code>analysisprotocol.samplepreparation.protocol(end).possibleamplitudeunits</code>. Choosing a unit here changes the value of <code>analysisprotocol.samplepreparation.protocol(end).amplitudeunits</code>. The first unit in <code>analysisprotocol.samplepreparation.protocol(end).possibleamplitudeunits</code> is the default value</p> <p>b. No choices are shown and the list is non-editable</p> <p>5. Almost all actions have a duration. There is should a free textbox allowing to enter the numerical value of <code>analysisprotocol.samplepreparation.protocol(end).duration</code>.</p> <p>6. The choices shown here are those from <code>internaldatabase.unitclass.time</code> and choosing one of these sets the property <code>analysisprotocol.samplepreparation.protocol(end).durationunits</code>.</p>				
12	Save as new sample preparation protocol	X	Button	If clicked, creates a new instance of <code>internaldatabase.standardmedium</code> . A pop-upwindow appears containing the steps contained in step 7 and 8
13	see all steps in Table 4 to add a new sample preparation protocol			⇒ <code>internaldatabase.sampleprep.samplepreparationprotocols</code> ⇒ <code>analysisprotocol.samplepreparation.samplepreparationprotocol</code>
14		MW	A non-editable list of the actions is also shown for the user to review what he/sje is to set as a standard sample preparation protocol	
15	Next		A button to go the next form. Also checks the sample preparation protocol for consistency, creates the property <code>analysisprotocol.preparesample</code> and saves the samplepreparation part.	At this step, the sample preparation is checked for consistency. An error that might occur is when <code>analysisprotocol.samplepreparation.protocol(end).endphase</code> can not be found amongst <code>analysisprotocol.combination.technique.possiblephases</code> . An error message should appear saying:

				<p>“The sample preparation protocol currently does not create a sample that can be measured using #analysisprotocol.combination.technique.name#. Please review the protocol.”</p> <p>Additionally, the property analysisprotocol.preparesample is created. Its properties are assigned as follows:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • phase: equal to analysisprotocol.samplepreparation.protocol(end).endphase • chemistry: There are two options depending on the the “amplitudeormedium” property of actions within analysisprotocol.samplepreparation.protocol <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ <i>All were “amplitude”:</i> preparesample.chemistry equals orginalsample.chemistry ○ <i>At least one action was “medium”.</i> preparesample.chemistry equals the “medium” property of the last action that had its “amplitudeormedium” property set to “medium”.
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Table 6. “Measurement technique”: Questions about the analysisprotocol, algorithm and endpoint.

Nr	Question	Type	Choices	Remark								
1	Which model of instrument was used?	FS	analysisprotocol.combination(x).technique.models AND a free text model should be allowed to enter (because our DB might lack some instrument models).	⇒analysisprotocol.techniquesettings.instrumentmodel								
2	Select from previously provided measurement protocols and/or provide specific details	MW	analysisprotocol.combination.standardprotocols [other] (the option to define the settings from scratch or to change the ones from the standard operating procedure must always be there)	⇒ analysisprotocol.techniquesettings.measurementprotocol If a standard operating procedure is selected, analysisprotocol.techniquesettings.settings equals the selected sop. If nothing is selected here, the first object within analysisprotocol.combination.standardprotocols is copied towards analysisprotocol.techniquesettings.settings								
3	Instrument settings											
<p>To define settings, a table should be shown.</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Nr</th> <th>Setting</th> <th>Value</th> <th>Units</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>2</td> <td>3 – 1N</td> <td>4 – 1N</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>The number of rows in this table equals those settings analysisprotocol.techniquesettings.settings for which there is a nonempty value (because this indicates they are relevant for this combination). All the cells within the table are then filled out with default values:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> just the number in the array analysisprotocol.techniquesettings.settings(x).name analysisprotocol.techniquesettings.settings(x).value analysisprotocol.techniquesettings.settings(x).units <p>The values of column 3 and 4 can be changed. The possible choices in these cells are</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> analysisprotocol.techniquesettings.settings(x).possiblesettings changing the value sets ⇒ analysisprotocol.techniquesettings.settings(end).value 					Nr	Setting	Value	Units	1	2	3 – 1N	4 – 1N
Nr	Setting	Value	Units									
1	2	3 – 1N	4 – 1N									

4. analysisprotocol.techniquesettings.settings(x).possibleunits changing the value sets ⇒ analysisprotocol.techniquesettings.settings(end).units

Data treatment

4 To define data treatment steps, a table should be shown.

Order	Algorithm parameter	Value	Units
1 - X	2 – 1N	3 – FN	4 - X

Initially one row is shown where only column one has a number 1, but at the bottom of the table there is a button “add another” to add more algorithm steps. The columns of the table hold the following choices and propertie values of the algorithm are drawn from it

1. just the number in the array. Noneditable
2. a list of all analysisprotocol.algorithms.name having the order equal to the value in column 1. Once one of these is selected, the analysisprotocol.algorithms(x).name is set and the non-editable unit in column 4 is filled.
3. A free, numerical text field. ⇒ analysisprotocol.algorithms(x).value
4. analysisprotocol.algorithms(x).units. Noneditable.

Table 7. A form to enter analysis data

Nr	Question	Type	Choices	Remark
Raw data				
1	Dataset template	1N	analysisprotocol.combination.possibledatasets.name or None	⇒ analysis.rawdataset Upon selecting one of the templates, it is copied to analysis.rawdataset The next steps depend on the number of objects in analysis.rawdataset.measurements.axes <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If None is chosen, go straight to step 16 • If only one (i.e. data is zerodimensional), go to step 2

				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> If more than one (i.e. data is one or multidimensional) go to step 4
2		FN	free text box where the single number can be added	⇒ analysis.rawdataset.measurement.axes.values
3		1N	analysis.rawdataset.measurements.axes.possibleunits	⇒ analysis.rawdataset.measurements.axes.units
4	Do you wish to upload raw data?	1N	Yes/No	If Yes, a pop-up window appears and a multidimensional data can be uploaded as described in Table 8
5	Measurement uncertainty Uncertainty type	1N	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> None internaldatabase.unitclass.uncertaintytypes 	If none is selected, skip to step 10 otherwise ⇒ analysis.rawdata.uncertaintytype Depending on
6	Uncertainty data organisation	1N	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> “single value” “text or spreadsheet” “image” “Output from instrument software” 	Depending on the answer: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> “One number” go step 7 otherwise go to step 9
7		FN	free text box where the single number can be added	only one axis object, analysis.rawdataset.uncertainty.axis, is created with <ul style="list-style-type: none"> uncertainty.axis.valueaxis is set to true uncertainty.axis.name is the same as analysis.rawdata.uncertaintytype ⇒ uncertainty.axis.value is retrieved from the text box
8		1N	analysis.rawdataset.measurements.axes.possibleunits	⇒ analysis.rawdataset.uncertainty.axis.units

9	Do you wish to upload uncertainty data?	1N	Yes/No	If Yes, a pop-up window appears and a multidimensional data can be uploaded as described in Table 8
10	Quality parameters Quality parameter type	1N	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> None internaldatabase.combination.relevantmeasurementqualityparameters 	If none is selected, skip to step 15 otherwise ⇒ analysis.rawdata.measurementqualityparameter
11	Quality parameter data organisation	1N	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> “single value” “text or spreadsheet” “image” “Output from instrument software”	Depending on the answer: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> “One number” go step 12 Otherwsie go to step 14
12		FN	free text box where the single number can be added	only one axis object, analysis.rawdataset.uncertainty.axis, is created with <ul style="list-style-type: none"> uncertainty.axis.valueaxis is set to true uncertainty.axis.name is the same as analysis.rawdata.uncertaintytype ⇒ uncertainty.axis.value is retrieved from the text box
13		1N	analysis.rawdataset.measremtnqualityparameter.axes.possibleunits	⇒ analysis.rawdataset.measremtnqualityparameter.axes.units
14	Do you wish to upload quality parameter data?	1N	Yes/No	If Yes, a pop-up window appears and a multidimensional data can be uploaded as described in Table 8
15	Detection limits Lower and upper LOD	FN	Number	⇒ endpoint.LODlower ⇒ endpoint.LODupper
Treated data				
16	Steps 1 – 15 are basically repeated for Treated data. The object is now analysis.treateddataset			

Table 8. A form to enter image, spreadsheet or data into an axes object. Used in Table 7.

Nr	Question	Type	Choices	Remark												
1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> If a spreadsheet or text file is imported, go to step 2 If an image is uploaded go to step 4 Instrument software output, go to step 5 															
2	<p>How is the data organised?</p> <p>A table is shown</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Axis</th> <th>Start column</th> <th>End column</th> <th>Start row</th> <th>End row</th> <th>Units</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>1 – 1W</td> <td>2 - FN</td> <td>3 - FN</td> <td>4 - FN</td> <td>5 - FN</td> <td>6 – 1W</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>The cells have as choices:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> All possible analysis.rawdataset.axes.names. The option [other] is there to type in a new, not previously defined axis ⇒ axes.startcolumn ⇒ axes.endcolumn ⇒ axes.startrow ⇒ axes.endrow To choose from axes.possibleunits. The option [other] is there to type in a new, not previously defined unit. ⇒ axes.unit <p>With this data, the data should be able to be exported towards their respective axes</p>	Axis	Start column	End column	Start row	End row	Units	1 – 1W	2 - FN	3 - FN	4 - FN	5 - FN	6 – 1W			
Axis	Start column	End column	Start row	End row	Units											
1 – 1W	2 - FN	3 - FN	4 - FN	5 - FN	6 – 1W											
3	Wat separation character is used	1N	<p>Choices are</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> tab komma semicolon space 	<p>⇒ axes.sepchar Now go to step 5</p>												

4	<p>How is the data organised in the image? A table is shown</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="219 331 757 405"> <thead> <tr> <th data-bbox="219 331 340 368">Axis</th> <th data-bbox="340 331 757 368">Units</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td data-bbox="219 368 340 405">1 – 1W</td> <td data-bbox="340 368 757 405">2 – 1W</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>The cells have as choices: All possible analysis.rawdataset.axes.names. The option [other] is there to type in a new, not previously defined axis To choose from analysis.rawdataset.axes.possibleunits. The option [other] is there to type in a new, not previously defined unit</p>			Axis	Units	1 – 1W	2 – 1W
Axis	Units						
1 – 1W	2 – 1W						
5	File location	FS	<p>A free textbox is followed by a button “browse” so the user can navigate to his/her file</p> <p>⇒ axes.file</p> <p>In the case of an image file or file from instrument software, the file is just stored inside the database without further processing. In the cae of a text file, the data is imported in the appropriate axis objects, based on the information of step 7 (start/end row/column as well as separation character)</p>				

Expert questionnaires

Table 9 lists all the endpoints/technique combinations that were added to the internal database in this first version of the knowledge warehouse. Also indicated is the partner that was deemed an expert in this particular combination. This partner was asked to provide all other parameters needed for the internal database, in terms of sample treatment, relevant instrument parameters and algorithm steps. For instance, it was asked to suggest new parameters and protocol actions that we did not think of ourselves. As an example of an output of the expert questionnaires, the final list of sample preparation from which users will be able to choose to describe their sample treatment is given in Table 10. The table describes the different properties of objects of the class “action” (See Table 2) that the user can add to their sample treatment protocol. It also describes what start and what endphase the action results into. This again serves to avoid errors in the protocol. The actions will have a certain order within the protocol. Actions following each other must be compatible with each other, meaning the beginphase of the next action must be compatible with the endphase of the previous action. That way, we avoid erroneous protocols where, for instance, a milling step, which occurs on and results in dry powders, is followed by shaking, which occurs on and results in an aqueous suspension.

The feedback from expert questionnaires is incorporated in the internal database. This database will be subject to constant change and will have to be curated in the future, e.g. when a new endpoint – technique combination emerges or certain developments, within ACEnano or elsewhere, call for changes to certain insights. The whole purpose of this meta-analysis is to ensure that such changes can occur without much effort, i.e. the core program does not need changing, only the internal database.

Table 9. List of endpoints and the included techniques capable of measuring them for which essential information will be collected within the lifetime of ACEnano, including the relevant expert partners

Endpoint	Possible Techniques	Expert
Batch dispersion/stability	DLS	MVN
Crystalline phase	XRD - crystalline phase	UOXF
	TEM	UOXF
Density	cF3	PNV
	Disc centrifuge	UoB
Elemental composition and chemical purity	SEM/TEM-EDX	UOXF
	ICP-MS	PE
	SP-TOF-ICP-MS	TOFW
	LA-ICP-MS	UFZ
Functional coating	TOF-SIMS	UFZ/JRC
	TERS	Horiba

	Raman	NERC
	MALDI-TOF	RIKILT
	STEM-EDS	UFZ
	XPS	BAM
	QCM-D	Biolin
	TGA-IR-GC/MS	PE
	CE	SCIEX
IsoElectric Point	Electrophoretic mobility	MVN
Average size dimension	DLS	MVN
	NTA	MVN
	SAXS	HYU/NCNST
	Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM)	UoB
	WAXD	HYU/NCNST
	XRD - Crystallite size	UOXF
	Mastersizer	Horiba
Particle Size Distribution	SP-ICP-MS	ETH
	Single-cell spICP-MS	PE
	TEM	UOXF
	SEM	UOXF
	AFM	Horiba
	NTA	MVN
	Disc centrifuge	JRC/UoB
	cF3	PNV
	aF4	PNV
	SEC/HDC/HIC	UFZ/Rikilt
	Mastersizer	Horiba
	CE	SCIEX

Particle shape	MALS/SLS	PNV
	SEM	UOXF
	TEM	UOXF
	AFM	Horiba
	Centrifugal FFF-MALS	MVN
	SAXS	HYU/NCNST
Solubility/dissolution	Ultrafiltration+ICP-MS	RIKILT
	Dialysis+ICP-MS	RIKILT
	Ultracentrifugation+ICP-MS	RIKILT
	Ion-selective electrode	?
	spICP-MS	ETH
	NTA	MVN
	assay-on-a-chip	CSEM
VSSA / porosity	BET analysis	BAM
	NMR relaxation	?
Z-potential	Electrophoretic mobility	MVN
Particle number concentration	spICP-MS	ETH
	NTA	MVN
	TEM	UOXF
	SEM	UOXF
	LIBD	CSEM
Homoaggregation rate	Time resolved DLS	MVN
	Time resolved spICPMS	UVIE
	Time resolved NTA	MVN
	CE	SCIEX
Deposition rate	Column test	SLU
	QCMD	Biolin

Hydrophobicity	HIC	Rikilt
	Dye loaded FFF	CSEM
	Assay-on-a-chip	CSEM
	Force tensiometry	CSEM/Biolin
Redox speciation	TEM-EELS	UOXF
	XANES	HYU/NCNST
	XPS	BAM
	TXM	HYU/NCNST
	STXM	HYU/NCNST
ROS generation	Assay-on-a-chip	CSEM
NP-cell interaction	QCMD	Biolin

Table 10. Actions and their properties.

Action name	Description	Example of how relevant	Amplitudes of the action other than the duration	(Class: Amplitude Units)	Duration relevant	Possible startphases	Possible endphases	Startphase = endphase? (Class:same phase)
Sonication	Breaks up aggregates with ultrasound. Can detach material from particles surfaces.	Reduces sizes of aggregates	Amplitude	Watt Joule	Y	aqueous solvent Biological fluid	aqueous solvent Biological fluid	Y
Shaking	Disperses particulate material. Speeds up dissolution of soluble compounds.	Induces aggregation	Shaking speed	'rpm'	Y	aqueous, solvent Biological fluid	aqueous, solvent Biological fluid	Y
Heating	Increases temperature. Increases rate of desorption, dissolution, oxidation and aggregation.	May alter crystallinity/ reduce porosity	Temperature	Celsius Kelvin Fahrenheit	Y	ALL	ALL	Y
Milling	Breaks up solids	Reduces sizes	Milling speed	rpm	Y	solid	solid	Y
Addition of chemicals	Often surfactants for increasing dispersion stability.	See question on sample chemistry	compounds	name/ concentration	N	ALL	ALL	Y

Incubation	Biological processes at slightly elevated temperatures	The same as heating	Temperature	Celsius Kelvin Fahrenheit	Y	ALL	ALL	Y
Drying	Evaporation of water/solvent in a sample.	Oxidation may occur	Temperature	Celsius Kelvin Fahrenheit	Y	ALL	solid tissue cells powder	N
Freezing	Freezing of water/solvent.	May cause aggregation	Temperature	Celsius Kelvin Fahrenheit	Y	ALL	solid tissue cells powder	N
Freeze-drying	Low pressure drying of sample at temperature below freezing point	May cause aggregation	Temperature	Celsius Kelvin Fahrenheit	Y	ALL	solid tissue cells powder	N
Filtration	Removal of particles with dimensions above a cut-off value.	Often results in large losses of nanoparticles also below the cut-off	Pore size	mm um nm kDa Da	N	aqueous solvent Biological fluid	aqueous solvent Biological fluid	Y
Extraction	Bringing a colloid into contact with another immiscible solvent. Particles are redistributed between the two media according to their hydrophobicity	May dissolve some nanoparticles	compounds	name/ concentration	N	solid tissue cells powder	aqueous solvent	N

Suspension	Dispersing particles into liquid (without sonication) to produce a suspension	May dissolve some nanoparticles	compounds	name/ concentration	N	solid tissue cells powder	aqueous solvent	N
Vortexing	The same as shaking, but done with a mechanical device.	May cause aggregation	Vortexing speed	rpm	Y	aqueous Solvent Biological fluid	aqueous solvent Biological fluid	Y
Protein Digestion	Digestion of proteins in the corona	Creates a protease digest to analyse	Protease concentration (compounds) Time and temperature of digestion	name/ concentration Celsius Kelvin Fahrenheit	Y	Aqueous solvent	Aqueous solvent	Y
Protein reduction	Reduction of proteins	Reduces cysteine bridges in proteins	Reduction agent. (compound) Temperature of reduction	name/ concentration Celsius Kelvin Fahrenheit	Y	Aqueous solvent	Aqueous solvent	Y
Protein alkylation	Alkylation of proteins	Alkylates cysteine residues to prevent reformation of cysteine bridges	Alkylation agent (compound) Time and temperature of reduction	name/ concentration Celsius	Y	Aqueous solvent	Aqueous solvent	Y

				Kelvin Fahrenheit Hours				
Peptide enrichment	Purifies and concentrates peptide	Remove remaining NPs, eliminates residual protease, desalts the sample and concentrates the samples	ZIP-TIP bed size	µg	N	Aqueous solvent	Aqueous/organic solvent mix	N
Dilution	Additional dilution of original sample for analysis	May cause dissolution, aggregation	Dilution factor	double	N	Aqueous solvent Biological fluid	Aqueous solvent Biological fluid	N All chemistry /compound/concentration are multiplied with dilution factor
Storage	The temperature and duration the sample is stored at i.e. room temperature or refrigerated, between initial sample and sample ready for analysis	Higher storage temperatures may cause aggregation	Temperature	Celsius Kelvin Fahrenheit	Y	ALL	ALL	Y
Density matching of fluid	Changing density of fluid to be a closer match to the particles	Closer matched densities reduces sedimentation	compounds	name/ concentration	N	aqueous solvent	aqueous solvent	Y

Langmuir-Blodgett trough monolayer deposition	Nanoparticles are dispersed at the air-liquid interface and further deposited onto a substrate with a trough going from a liquid environment to a dry state.	The change of state may change the nature of the nanoparticles such as stabilizing coating.	Deposition rate	mm·s ⁻¹	N	aqueous solvent	Solid	N
Cell pretreatments	Processes performed to cells prior to NM treatment to perform different types of experiments	Serum starvation can change protein content of media / cells siRNA inhibition requires siRNA transfection steps that inhibit uptake pathways Colocalization studies requires DNA transfection steps to incorporate fluorescent protein into the cells	Cell pretreatment Protocol	string	Y	Cells Biological tissue	Cells Biological tissue	Y
Addition of proteins to the dispersion / incubation with proteins	Addition of serum proteins to buffer or media	Proteins and small molecules can bind to the NM surface leading to increases in size, changes in agglomeration, changes in charge and surface chemistry	Concentration and composition of proteins (array of compound) source, lot numbers	name/ concentration string	N	Cells	Cells	Y

				array of double				
Cell exposure to NM	Cells can be exposed in a variety of different methods: transwell (Liquid/liquid), transwell (air/liquid), upright, inverted. Cells can also be in adherent culture (2D/3D) or in suspension Well plate format	Different exposure configurations will lead to different NM exposure (based on NM properties / buoyant NMs, NMs that sediment quickly etc) and therefore modify effects. Different well plates have different effects on diffusion and sedimentation	Exposure configuration (upright etc.) Cell configuration (2D/3D) Well plate configuration (6 well etc, round or flat) Volume of media added Material of container Number of doses NM type Concentration of dose. (compound)	string string string mL string double string double	Y	cells	cells	Y
Fixation with formaldehyde	Use of chemical compounds to form crosslinks between cell components and deactivating proteolytic enzymes	Formaldehyde breaks down to an acidic product which may alter pH and modify the dissolution of NMs. Fixation causes significant crosslinking which may modify	pH PFA concentration (compound)	double name/concentration	Y	Cells	Cells	Y

		NM chemistry and surrounding matrix Fixation permeabilises cell membranes which may lead to loss of sample or gain of sample or interferences						
Staining	Staining cells with fluorescent dyes	May interact with NMs or bind NMs leading to a decrease in concentration of NMs available. May alter cell health if not appropriately controlled	Dye composition (compound)	name/concentration	Y	Cells	Cells	Y
Mounting	Mounting onto coverslips/slides	Changes the refractive index of cells. Has to be matched closely as possible and optimized for visualizing reflectant signal	Type of media, RI of media	string double	N	Cells	Cells	Y

User interface

Figures 2-6 shows screenshots from the final user interface, from opening the application to submitting an analysis protocol. These figures are a direct translation of Tables 2-8 into code. Some differences may be noted. The user interface is constantly under update based on feedback from partners so the final version could not yet be shown.

- In the first step (Figure 2) the user is informed about what is required for completing a database entry and thus given a chance to prepare the relevant data.
- The second sheet (Figure 3) is a direct implementation of Table 4. The user begins by entering all known relevant information about the sample chemistry, and any preparation procedure carried out prior to analysis. In this case the user has vortexed and sonicated the sample and reported the intensity of these actions as 500 rounds per minute and 47 kHz. The duration was stated as 30 s and 5 minutes (Figure 3). The sample preparation procedure can be saved as a standard protocol for future use.
- Figure 5 is an implementation of Table 6. The user has to enter the measured value for the endpoint, any relevant instrument parameters, and the data treatment procedures and algorithms employed (Figure 5). In the final step, the user has the chance to review the data before submitting it (Figure 6).
- Data entering (Table 7) has not yet been implemented as it has to be coupled with other aspects fo the ontology of later deliverables of WP 4.

Figure 2. The intro page of the DB user interface. Note that the irrelevant random text will be replaced with actual text when the DB is filled with actual protocols.

Add protocol

1 General info ✓
2 Sample preparation
3 Measurement
4 Preview & save

Original sample description

Phase

----- ▾

Medium

Select from standard media and/or provide specific details

----- ▾

Compound name	Concentration	Units ▾
Compound name	Concentration	Units ▾
...

+ Add another

pH ▾ 7

Ionic strength ▾ ...

... ▾ ...

+ Add another

Save as new medium

Sample pretreatment

Sample preparation protocol

Select from previously provided protocols and/or provide specific details

----- ▾

	Action name	Amplitude/setting?	Amplitude	Units	Duration	Units	Start phase
1	Vortexing ▾	Vortexing speed ▾	500	rpm ▾	30	s ▾	Aqueous liquid ▾
2	Sonication ▾	Frequency ▾	47	kHz ▾	5	min ▾	Aqueous liquid ▾

+ Add another

Save as new sample preparation protocol

Go to next step

If media is selected from our DB, the below fields can be pre-filled, with an option to edit if needed.

User needs to provide a name, if the medium is saved as new medium to the DB

This section is shown only if sample was pretreated.

Previously added protocols can be selected from our DB. In this case the below fields can be pre-filled, with an option to edit if needed.

Figure 3. The second user interface page where information on sample properties and preparation should be entered.

Add protocol

1 General 1 **Sample preparation** 2 Measurement technique 3 Data treatment

Save sample preparation protocol

Name

Brief description

Protocol version

Version: Variant: Derived from:

Actions

	Action name	Amplitude name	Amplitude	Amplitude units	Duration	Duration unit	Startphase	Endphase
1	Vortexing	Vortexing speed	500	rpm	30	s	Aqueous liquid	Aqueous liquid
2	Sonication	Frequency	47	kHz	5	min	Aqueous liquid	Aqueous liquid

Sample pretreatment

Sample preparation protocol

Select from previously provided protocols and/or provide specific details

	Action name	Amplitude/setting?	Amplitude	Units	Duration	Units	Start phase	End phase
1	Vortexing	Vortexing speed	500	rpm	30	s	Aqueous liquid	Aqueous liquid
2	Sonication	Frequency	47	kHz	5	min	Aqueous liquid	Aqueous liquid

+ Add another

User can choose to save the sample preparation protocol. This protocol then becomes available for reuse in other protocols.

Figure 4. The user is given the option to save the reported sample preparation steps as a standard protocol.

Add protocol

1 General info ✓
2 Sample preparation ✓
3 Measurement
4 Preview & save

Endpoints measured, techniques used

+ Add another

Which model of instrument was used?

Instrument settings

Setting 1	Value	Unit
Setting 2	Value	Unit
...

+ Add another

Data treatment

Algorithm used for extracting endpoint

Was data edited?

Were manual data analysis procedures employed?

Measurement

Value

Uncertainty

Limit of detection (LOD)

Measurement quality parameters

+ Add another

In this step the user enters the measurement results and relevant parameters

Figure 5. The user will enter the measured value for the endpoint and relevant instrument parameters and data analysis procedures.

Add protocol

1 General info ✓ 2 Sample preparation ✓ 3 Measurement ✓ 4 Preview & save

General information

Show provided data ...

Sample preparation

Show provided data ...

Measurement

Show provided data ...

Submit Make more changes

The user has the chance to review the results before submitting the data

Figure 6. The user is given a chance to review the data before submitting it.

Glossary of terms

This section contains a list of terms or abbreviations with their definition (and definition source if available), used in the context of ACEnano project and its infrastructure development.

- ACEnano = Analytical and Characterisation Excellence in nanomaterial risk assessment: A tiered approach (EU H2020 Project 2017-2020)
- aF4 = Asymmetrical field flow fractionation
- AOP = Adverse Outcome Pathway
- API = Application Programming Interface
- APS = Aerodynamic Particle Sizer
- ATR-FTIR = Attenuated total reflection -Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy
- BET = Brunauer–Emmett–Teller (BET) theory aims to explain the physical adsorption of gas molecules on a solid surface. It serves as the basis for an important analysis technique to measure the specific surface area of a material
- CE = capillary electrophoresis
- cF3 = Centrifugal field flow fractionation
- CLS = Centrifugal Liquid Sedimentation
- COV = Calculated coefficient of variation
- CRM = Certified Reference Material
- DB = Database
- DI = De-ionised (water)
- DLS = Dynamic Light Scattering
- EDX = Energy-Dispersive X-ray spectroscopy
- FAIR = Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Re-usable
- FFF = Field flow fractionation
- FMPS = Fast Mobility Particle Size
- GLP = Good Laboratory Practice
- HEPA = High-Efficiency Particulate Air (filter)
- HIC = Hydrophobic interaction chromatography
- ICP-MS = Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry
- ICP-OES = Inductively Coupled Plasma Optical Emission Spectrometry
- IEP = IsoElectric Point
- ISO = International Organisation for Standardization
- IUPAC = International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry
- KI = Knowledge Infrastructure
- KW = Knowledge Warehouse
- LDE = Laser Doppler Electrophoresis
- LIBD = Laser induced breakdown detection
- MALDI-TOF = Matrix-Assisted Laser Desorption/Ionization
- MNP = Manufactured NanoParticle
- NM = Nanomaterial
- NMR = Nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy
- NSC = NanoSafety Cluster
- NTA = Nanoparticle tracking analysis
- OECD = Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development
- QCM-D = Quartz crystal microbalance with dissipation monitoring
- RDF = Resource Description Framework

- REST = Representational State Transfer
- RMN = Representative Manufactured Nanomaterial
- ROS = Reactive Oxygen Species
- RSD = Relative Standard Deviation
- RTM = Representative Test Material
- SAXS = Small-Angle X-ray Scattering
- SD = Standard Deviation
- SEC = Size exclusion chromatography
- SEM = Scanning Electron Microscopy
- SERS = Surface enhanced raman scattering
- SMPS = Scanning Mobility Particle Sizer
- SOP = Standard Operating Procedure
- SP-ICP-MS = Single Particle Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry
- SP-TOF-ICP-MS = Single Particle Time of flight Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry
- SSA = Specific Surface Area
- STEM-EDS = Scanning Transmission Electron Microscope- Energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy
- STXM = Scanning transmission X-ray microscopy
- TEM = Transmission Electron Microscopy
- TEM-EELS = Transmission electron microscopy with electron energy loss spectroscopy
- TGA = Thermogravimetric Analysis
- TOF-SIMS = Time of flight secondary ion mass spectrometry
- TXM = Full field transmission X-ray microscopy
- UV-VIS = Ultraviolet-visible Spectrophotometry
- VSSA = Volume Specific Surface Area
- w/w% = Weight percent
- WAXD = Wide-Angle X-ray Scattering
- WDXRF = Wavelength Dispersive X-ray Fluorescence
- WP = Workpackage
- XANES = X-ray absorption near edge spectroscopy
- XPS = X-ray photon spectroscopy
- XRD = X-Ray Diffraction